

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

A STRATEGIC PLANNING HIERARCHY FRAMEWORK ON AN EXAMPLE OF THE IMPACT OF THE PENSION BACK-PAYMENT SYSTEM¹

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Abstract

The concept of healthy and active longevity gained worldwide recognition in the late 1980s. According to geriatricians, it includes physical health, financial security, efficiency and employment, independence, optimism, involvement in public life. It should be noted with a historical overview that if the newly independent RA adopted a policy aimed only at the satisfaction of social needs of the elderly, in particular, material security, now we accept that the spectrum of the needs of the elderly population should be considered more multi-layered and diverse, due to the increase of information on the experience of modern developed countries, the increase of the level of consciousness of people and other factors. It enables people to realize and use their physical, social and intellectual potential throughout life according to their preferences and capabilities.

The optimization process requires consistent work, and the current reality in Armenia can provide real foundations for the realization of the vision of complete development, because the already formed program package provides the opportunity from the point of view of effective assessment of strategic processes, it can and should be complemented by justified approaches to universal demand in order to ensure the comprehensive conditions necessary for the normal life of the public.

Keywords: social protection sphere, pension system, aging problems, program package, comprehensiveness.

The purpose of the interweaving of what was and what is desired based on stability in a safe environment is to ensure the inclusive well-being of civil society.

The state budget first of all expresses the tax-budgetary policy, which can be considered as effective if it provides such system of distribution and redistribution of public funds, which on the one hand would guarantee the development of the economy, and on the other hand, would guarantee the effective addressing of social and security needs. [1]

During the recent years, the planning of budget allocations in RA has been greatly influenced by the continuous growth of both initially “unknown-unknown” and “known-unknown” risks (post-covid, post-war period). In the first case, the events are objectively outside the scope of planning-performance accountability, in the second case, the planning of the “fiscal area” or the planning of stabilizing account over the time can reduce the probability of planning deviation as a result of the materialization of little-known risks only by the implementation of current measures (preventive and/or overcoming) in part, while the new realities, for example, the solution of the problems of the “existence + living” programs of more than 100,000 Artsakh Armenians, the compensation of damages caused by the flooding of the Debet and Aghstev rivers, and restoration works (transportation network,

residential areas, gardens and other infrastructures), imply a systematic approach to planning budget allocations, also at the social and international levels.

The positive changes in the macro-indicators providing the fiscal principles recorded in the current period allow us to predict that in the following years, from the point of view of overcoming the multi-layered crisis, in the case of a review of the organization of the budgetary processes, we can return to the approaches of equal adjustment of financial indicators and non-financial indicators, initially from a methodological point of view, giving more importance in the context of strategic planning to the definition of aggregated indicators in the policy-principles-policy review chain.

Armenia has appeared on the upper threshold of aging societies. Projections of the United Nations Population Fund show that in 2050, people over 65 will make up 22-23% of the population. [2] Since 2012, within the framework of a strategic approach, the possibilities of overcoming mobility deficits among the elderly and promoting the organization of volunteer work, self-activities have been considered, aligning the current RA legislation regulating the field with the “Regional Implementation Strategy of the Madrid International Action Plan on Aging Problems” and other international legal acts. [3] Still in the 2022 report, a number of priorities were highlighted, such as ensuring the health and active lifestyle of the elderly, maintaining health, independence and dignity in old age, creating sufficient foundations for ensuring a longer working life for the elderly, etc. [4]

¹ pension: the amount specified in point 3 of Decision N 284- N of the Government of the Republic of Armenia of March 12, 2020: pensions expected by social protection (security) programs, periodic benefits (given for a definite or indefinite period) and other monetary payments

1.3 goal[5] of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations of 2030 states, "To introduce appropriate social protection systems and measures for all in the given country, including social protection guarantee groups, and by 2030 to reach the "inclusion of the poor and vulnerable in a significant degree», and according to the Strategy of Transformation of Armenia: "By 2050, we should make a healthy lifestyle a national characteristic, increase the expected life duration to 90 years". 1 of the 16 mega-goals to be implemented in the next 10 years states: «Through widespread, inclusive, innovative and accessible development and assimilation of knowledge, culture, awareness, skills, we should have a civilized, creative, initiative, capable and competitive citizen, for whom the realization of rights is equally important as much as the fulfillment of duties and obligations, who first of all considers himself responsible for his own well-being and health. [6]

In order to achieve a sustainable growth of 7%, the RA government will continue investing additional efforts in the way of investments in human and physical

capital, effective implementation of strategies aimed at promoting private investments, employment and exports, as well as increasing the efficiency of the state system and the quality of services provided to the public. In the medium-term period (2025-2027), the tax-budgetary policy will be aimed at guaranteeing the smooth process of reforms, strengthening the economy's resilience and increasing its growth potential through a significant increase in the level of investments in economic and protective infrastructures, human capital. From the viewpoint of increasing the effectiveness of the spending policy, the purposeful, economical and efficient use of public finances is important. In terms of increasing the targeting of expenditures, a transition will be made to strategic planning, and in order to increase the effectiveness and usefulness of spending programs, a regular process of evaluating budget programs will be introduced. The spending policy with additional initiatives and systemic reforms in education, health and social protection will be aimed at the most effective development and realization of human capital.

Table 1.

Financing Volumes of Large Programs, 2024. [7]

Program classifier	Program name	Amount (thousand drams)	Share in total costs, %	Structure, %
Financing of 10 Programs		2 084 296 159,6	69,08	100
1- 1169	Provision of protection of RA	549 931 131,6	18,23	26,38
2-1102	Pension provision	471 441 832,0	15,62	22,62
3-1006	Public debt management	322 225 518,2	10,68	15,46
4-1146	General education program	124 301 639,0	4,12	5,96
5- 1049	Road network improvement	119 198 703,2	3,95	5,72
6-1212	Territorial development	109 859 638,6	3,64	5,27
7-1205	Social security	108 627 343,4	3,60	5,21
8-1236	Education ²	96 801 415,0	3,21	4,64
9-1139	Reserve fund ³	93 995 935,9	3,12	4,51
10-1234	MIA ⁴	87 913 002,7	2,91	4,22
Total budget		3 017 259 848,0	100	x

The supremacy of the social sphere conditioned by the volume of funding is reflected in Table 1. according

to the functional classification, also according to the distribution of programs.

² Establishment, construction and improvement of general education and preschool institutions

³ Reserve fund of the Government of RA

⁴ The elaboration of policy, management, centralized measures , monitoring and control of the sphere of the RA Ministry of Internal Affairs

Table 2.

Expenditures on spending programs of the RA 2024 social sphere and social protection budget according to functional classification, (thousand drams) [8]

	Social sphere	1 259 291 971,2	100 %
1.	HEALTH	170 722 085,3	13.6
2.	REST, CULTURE AND RELIGION	40 544 373,1	3.2
3.	EDUCATION	292 740 660,1	23.2
4.	SOCIAL PROTECTION	755 284 852,7	60.0
	including:		<i>of which</i>
	Bad health and incapacity	2 444 335,8	0.2
	Old age (<i>also program 1205</i>)	527 466 572,1	41.9
	Persons who have lost their relatives (<i>also-1205</i>)	4 856 000,0	0.4
	Family members and children (<i>also-1205</i>)	115 821 754,2	9.2
	Unemployment	608 417,7	0.0
	Housing	4 017 494,5	0.3
	Special social benefits (not belonging to other classes)	12 408 830,0	1.0
	Social protection (not belonging to other classes) (<i>also-1205</i>)	87 661 448,4	7.0

As in 2024, in the medium term, it is planned that the expenses of the social sector will make more than 40 percent of the total expenses, of which the social

protection sector will vary between 25-26 percent, crossing the threshold of 1 trillion drams in 2027.

Figure 1: Weight in the total sector budget %, 2024

Programs of the Social protection sector are arranged according to 2024 funding volumes (descending). As noted in the Citizen's budget, 795.3 billion drams are allocated to Social protection programs, of which around 494 billion drams or 62.1% are allocated to Pension security (1102), 113 billion drams or 14.2% to Social security (1205), and 68.9 billion drams or 8.7% to the Improvement of the demographic situation (1068).

The following steps to be undertaken until 2026 are presented in Labor and Social Protection subsection 4.6 of the Human Capital Section of the RA Government's activity program:

- To equalize the minimum pension and the average pension to the values of the food and consumer baskets, respectively.

- To set the minimum salary at 85,000 AMD
- To eliminate extreme poverty. [9]

At the beginning of 2023, according to WB's assessment, the size of food and consumer baskets made 38,576.5 and 72,072.7 AMD, respectively.[10]

According to the data of the Statistical Committee, the levels of poverty and extreme poverty in 2023 made 23.7 (the upper poverty line is 64,146 AMD, average is 53,590, by checking with the WB) and 1.1 percent (29,786 AMD), respectively decreasing by 1.1% and 0.1% compared to the previous year. As compared with the previous ten years, the levels of poverty and extreme poverty decreased by 8.3% (39193 AMD) and 1.6% (22993 AMD).[11]

Beneficiaries of social protection programs of the state are directly related to high inflation phenomena, as a result of which the solvency of consumers decreases, and the problem is more aggravated for the beneficiaries of vulnerable groups, in particular, in terms of acquiring essential items and food. Deflationary trends were registered in January-May of 2024. The deflationary environment was formed due to the significant weakening of the inflationary pressures transmitted from the world economy, the increase of exchange rate, as well as due to the lag effect of consistent accommodative monetary policy

implemented in 2020-2022. As a result, the 12-month inflation made 0.3% in May, the average inflation made -0.8% in January-May. [12] Despite these short-term developments, the objective basis for long-term planning is the consideration of the possibilities of extrapolation of inflation indicators.

Under the current conditions of the economy, expected by the program of the RA government along with the target increases of pensions, allowances or other monetary payments there is a need to implement measures aimed at the increase of purchasing power also with other tools. [13] Within the framework of the transfer measure 12029 of the Social Security 1205 program, the provision of a 10% back-payment of non-cash payments to pensioners starting from July 1, 2022 is presented (now more than 10 billion AMD). It should also be noted that in 2024 from September 1, citizens using the pension and benefit back-payment program will be given the opportunity to receive a maximum of AMD 6000 (12%) instead of the previous AMD 5000 (10%) from non-cash payments for the purchase of goods and/or services. [14] The goal of the 1205 program is to ensure the implementation of the right to social security [15], the final result is the percentage of allowances in case of old age, disability, loss of a breadwinner in relation to the food basket, the baseline indicator of which is 82.3, and it will reach 100 percent in the target period of 2026. [16]

Outlining the back-payment transfer measure for pensioners from the current measures on overcoming extreme poverty, it should be noted that the impact of the latter is significant from the point of view of the Program budgeting system in the context of "bottom-up" planning. The determination of the general directions of development is more realistic from the point of view of the general solution of problems, and the implementation of individual equivalent measures requires not only thorough work, but also a high degree of accuracy. As part of the budget programs, the mentioned tool ensures a high level of metrics both from a tactical and a strategic point of view, and has wide opportunities for quantitative and qualitative measurement.

Although half of the beneficiaries still do not use the mentioned tool, if we spread the sub-program to higher levels, from the point of view of the hierarchy, it intersects with all the levels, as, for example, the relationship with the goals and sub-goals of the RA government's activity program:

Goal - To create a favorable and healthy environment for elderly people, ensuring their dignified aging process,

Sub-goals – The provision of legal bases and regulations for elderly people to stay longer in working life or encouragement and promotion of creative activities, etc. [17]

Despite the changes in some of the wordings of the legal regulations that are no longer in effect, the content logic of the above sub-goals/problems remains the same from the point of view of the solution in the next decades. The next level of the hierarchy is the mid-level strategic documents and budgetary program strategies, which logically include the most practical formulations

of the above-mentioned goals and objectives. At the indicator level, for example, this tool can be affected by the following indicator: the number of the families which receive social and psychological support has increased. It should be noted that apart from the upward connection of policies and measures, the back-payment tool is connected with both the social protection sphere and related social spheres (health care, education, sports, etc.).

The methodological manual for defining gender-sensitive budget programs mentions data that do not exist in Armenia, in particular, the percentage of the adult population who are entrepreneurs, the indicator by gender, etc., although, for example, the proportion of women and men who use cash transfers is mentioned. [18] In addition, the continuous provision of back-payments to pensioners will further contribute analytically, going beyond the scope of comparison and interaction of the various indicators of budget programs, to the discussion of volume-structural changes in the directions of the use of the pension, directing it also to the exclusion of even a small impact on economic indicators (for example, inflation), because the improvement of consumer's behavior supposes the formation of reasonable demand.

Conclusion: From the study of international experience, we can draw conclusions that the results of the large-scale work done in the Program budgeting system in our country in terms of preventing the most unlikely risks, as well as the inhibition mechanisms of the formation of cause-and-effect problematic links, while taking into account the conclusions arising from the peculiarities of our budget system. Over the years, revisions for the improvement of the formats of the budget programs by the spending units responsible for the implementation of the public order have been a necessary but not sufficient condition, because the unilateralism at the beginning of this process did not balance the progress of the stages of the budget process in the context of provision of efficiency and effectiveness, and only for the following years have become predictable not only the trends of goal orientation, but also the expanding domains of methodological justifications. [19]

Summarizing the above it should be noted that under the risks outlined in the article, it is true that with the minimum delay in funding, the initiatives and measures that provide the maximum comprehensiveness are also delayed, as well as the issues of the reconstruction of our country's economy are considered in the field of foreign policy, being based on the indisputable need to establish security. This is conditioned by the importance of the existence, development and prosperity of our state at many points of intersection of territorial intersections under the current conditions of geopolitical developments. It can be stated that it is already perceived by all the interested states and international organizations as the organization of effective and useful public work with the purpose of realization of universal interest.

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